

Enhanced Metabolite Mapping via ChEBI Ontology

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Summary

Metabolomics datasets often fail to map to Reactome pathways due to systematic differences in chemical specificity between experimental annotations and pathway curation. LC-MS and GC-MS platforms typically report metabolites at a generic level (e.g. undefined stereochemistry or ionization state), whereas Reactome represents pathway participants using highly specific ChEBI identifiers. This mismatch causes many biologically relevant experimental signals to remain unmapped.

Here, we present an ontology-driven workflow that exploits the relational structure of the ChEBI ontology to expand each detected metabolite into a controlled set of chemically equivalent or closely related identifiers. The approach integrates chemical equivalence relationships, limited to a specialization, and ontology-based generalisation to progressively increase pathway coverage while maintaining chemical interpretability.

Applied to multiple public metabolomics datasets, this workflow approximately doubles the number of metabolites mapping to Reactome and yields a two- to three-fold increase in associated pathways compared to RefMet-based mapping alone. The results also highlight chemical classes, particularly lipids, that remain under-represented in pathway annotation, motivating targeted curation and closer integration between metabolomics resources and pathway databases.

1. Introduction

A recurring challenge in metabolomics pathway analysis is the semantic mismatch between analytical outputs and pathway knowledge bases.

- Analytical platforms (LC-MS, GC-MS) typically report compounds in generic form, without stereochemical resolution and often without explicit annotation of protonation states.
- Reactome, by design, annotates pathways using specific, physiologically relevant chemical entities, each represented by a unique ChEBI identifier.

This “specificity gap” results in widespread under-mapping when standard workflows attempt direct ID matching. Thus, valuable information in metabolomics datasets may be lost because the assayed metabolite identities cannot be mapped to relevant Reactome pathways.

Example: Lactic Acid

Automated name-standardization tools such as RefMet (https://www.metabolomicsworkbench.org/databases/refmet/name_to_refmetID_form.php) may assign Lactic acid (CHEBI:78320).

However:

- Reactome does not use this parent term.
- Instead, it annotates reactions with the specific bioactive forms:
 - (S)-lactic acid (CHEBI:422)
 - (S)-lactate (CHEBI:16651)
 - (R)-lactate (CHEBI:16004)

Thus, even though the experimental observation is correct, the metabolite fails to map to a Reactome pathway purely due to differences in chemical granularity rather than biological irrelevance.

Goal of the Workflow

To address this, we developed a semantic expansion workflow that uses the structure of the ChEBI Ontology to bridge the gap between typical analytical identifiers and Reactome’s specific curation requirements.

By treating certain ontology relationships as biologically equivalent for the purposes of a typical metabolomic pathway analysis, we enable:

1. broader but still chemically accurate matching,
2. improved pathway coverage, and
3. reduced false negatives leading to greater use of experimental data.

2. Methodology

Throughout this work, the term mapping refers specifically to the assignment of at least one Reactome pathway to a compound via a valid ChEBI identifier.

2.1 Datasets

As exemplars, data from three typical metabolomics studies were employed [1], [2], [3]. The details of each are reported in the following table

Table 1: Overview of metabolite annotation and Reactome pathway coverage for three example datasets, restricted to compounds that could be resolved through RefMet standardization.

Dataset	Number of compounds	Number of compounds with ChEBI	Number of compounds mapping to Reactome	Number of pathways	Average pathways per metabolite	Average metabolites per pathway
Covid-19 [1]	1029	685	114	478	12.02	2.84
IBD [2]	473	325	81	389	13.59	2.83
QMDiab [3]	404	346	84	412	12.02	2.44

2.2 Workflow

Figure 1: Ontology-based workflow for enhanced metabolite-to-Reactome mapping.

2.2.1 Data Standardization (RefMet Integration)

All datasets (e.g. COVID-19, IBD, etc.) were first processed using RefMet, which harmonizes metabolite names and assigns initial ChEBI identifiers. The outputs of RefMet serve as the input list of metabolites for our ontology-based workflow.

2.2.2 ChEBI Identifier Completion

As shown in *Figure 1*, many metabolites still lacked ChEBI identifiers even after RefMet standardization. To address this, we performed a secondary lookup against the **full ChEBI ontology**, querying **all ChEBI terms using both their primary names and associated synonyms**. Both RefMet-standardized metabolite names and the original input names from the datasets were used as queries. This step expanded the number of metabolites with valid ChEBI identifiers, improving baseline coverage and ensuring that the subsequent ontology traversal operates on the broadest possible set of starting nodes.

Figure 2: Identifier completion via ChEBI ontology lookup. Blue bars denote metabolites assigned a ChEBI identifier through RefMet standardization. Orange bars indicate metabolites without a RefMet-assigned ChEBI that were successfully resolved by the ontology lookup. Red bars represent metabolites that remained unassigned after both procedures.

2.2.3 Construction of Metabolite Chemical Equivalence Classes

For each metabolite with a ChEBI ID, we constructed a **Chemical Equivalence Class** representing all chemically related forms that may correspond to the same analytical signal in LC-MS or GC-MS assays.

We used four Relation Ontology (RO) relationships representing transformations or forms that are usually indistinguishable in a typical metabolomic assay:

- RO:0018033 — is_conjugate_base_of
- RO:0018034 — is_conjugate_acid_of
- RO:0018036 — is_tautomer_of
- RO:0018039 — is_enantiomer_of

2.2.4 Specialization via Hierarchical is_a Relationships

For each metabolite-associated ChEBI identifier, we performed a single-step traversal of the ChEBI *is_a* hierarchy to include its immediate descendant terms. **Each descendant was treated as a more specific representation of the original metabolite. For every descendant, the corresponding chemical equivalence class was generated.** The original ChEBI term, its immediate descendants, and all associated equivalence-class members were then evaluated for Reactome pathway mapping.

To summarize the cumulative effect of chemical equivalence expansion (Section 2.2.3) and hierarchical is_a refinement (Section 2.2.4), we visualized the combined contribution of these two steps to ChEBI-based metabolite coverage and Reactome mappability. The figure below illustrates how successive ontology-driven expansions at the ChEBI level increase the number of metabolites and pathways that can be associated with Reactome. Importantly, these steps operate by refining metabolite representation through chemically equivalent forms and more specific ChEBI terms, while preserving the identity of the original compounds. This contrasts with the ontology-based generalisation step described in Section 2.2.5, which departs from individual compound identities and maps remaining unmapped metabolites to broader chemical classes.

■ Reactome-mapped via RefMet-assigned ChEBI ■ Reactome-mapped via is_a refinement
■ Reactome-mapped via ChEBI name/synonym lookup ■ Has ChEBI but no Reactome pathway
■ Reactome-mapped via RO chemical equivalence ■ No ChEBI (cannot be mapped)

Figure 3: Percentage of metabolites associated with Reactome pathways at successive stages of the ontology-based expansion workflow across three datasets. Bars show the proportion of metabolites that become Reactome-mappable following successive ChEBI-based annotation and expansion steps. Blue segments represent metabolites associated with Reactome pathways via RefMet-assigned ChEBI identifiers. Orange segments indicate metabolites that gained Reactome associations after ChEBI identifier recovery through synonym- and name-based ontology lookup. Purple segments denote metabolites that became Reactome-mappable following RO-based chemical equivalence expansion (conjugate acid/base forms, tautomers, and enantiomers). Green segments represent metabolites that gained Reactome associations exclusively through single-step hierarchical is_a refinement to more specific ChEBI terms. Grey segments indicate metabolites that possess valid ChEBI identifiers but lack Reactome pathway annotations, while red segments represent metabolites for which no ChEBI identifier could be assigned and therefore cannot be mapped to Reactome.

Figure 4: Total number of unique Reactome pathways recovered at each stage of the ontology expansion workflow for the three datasets. Blue bars show pathways mapped directly through RefMet-assigned ChEBI identifiers. Orange bars represent additional pathways gained from metabolites whose ChEBI identifiers were recovered through the synonym/name-based lookup step. Purple bars correspond to pathways added via RO-based chemical equivalence expansion (conjugate acid/base forms, tautomers, enantiomers). Green bars show pathways uniquely contributed by is_a-based hierarchical generalisation, where mapping to more general ancestral structures revealed additional pathway annotations.

2.2.5 Ontology-Based Generalisation of Remaining Unmapped Compounds

For metabolites that remain unmapped after the previous expansion steps (gray bars in Fig.3), the workflow performs **an ontology-driven generalisation procedure**. In this step, the algorithm **ascends** the ChEBI hierarchy via **is_a parent relationships** to identify the nearest ancestor(s) that possess valid Reactome pathway annotations.

To maintain biological relevance, traversal is constrained by **excluding a predefined set of high-level ChEBI classes**, including *chemical entity* (CHEBI:24431), *molecular entity* (CHEBI:23367), and *nucleobase-containing molecular entity* (CHEBI:33838). These excluded classes were **manually selected based on their position at the top of the ChEBI hierarchy and their lack of biochemical specificity**, rather than being defined by a fixed distance from the ontology root. Additional exclusions can be made if required.

When multiple equidistant ancestor terms possess Reactome pathway annotations, all such ancestors are retained, thereby capturing the full set of minimal-distance biochemical parent classes.

Because ontology-based generalisation may reduce compound-level specificity, a PDF report is generated for each dataset to ensure transparency. For every generalised metabolite, the report documents the original compound and all intermediate ChEBI terms encountered during hierarchy traversal, up to the ancestor term that enables Reactome mapping.

Figure 5: Compounds that remained unmapped after earlier steps were processed through an ontology-based generalisation procedure, which ascends the ChEBI *is_a* hierarchy to identify the nearest ancestor(s) with valid Reactome pathway annotations. The bar chart shows, for each dataset, the number of compounds entering this stage and the proportion successfully mapped versus those still unmapped after generalization.

As described earlier, only compounds that fail to map through more specific chemical representations or through acid/base, tautomeric, or enantiomeric relationships are subjected to ontology-based generalisation and are illustrated in Figure 5.

To present the complete outcome of the proposed workflow, the cumulative results are summarised in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Cumulative Reactome mapping outcomes across ontology expansion and generalisation steps for the Covid-19, IBD, and QMDiab datasets (percentages are relative to the total number of compounds per dataset). Stacked bars show the proportion of compounds that gain **Reactome pathway annotations via successive ChEBI-based procedures: direct mapping through **RefMet-assigned ChEBI identifiers** (blue), additional mappings obtained through **ChEBI name/synonym lookup** (orange), **RO-based chemical equivalence expansion** (purple), and **one-step is_a refinement** to more specific descendants (green). For compounds still lacking pathway annotations after these steps, **ontology-based generalisation** ascends the ChEBI is_a hierarchy to the nearest annotated ancestor(s), enabling additional Reactome mapping (cyan). Remaining compounds with an assigned ChEBI but **no Reactome pathway even after generalisation** are shown in grey, while compounds with **no ChEBI identifier** (and therefore not mappable to Reactome) are shown in red.**

The final improvements are also reported compared to the mapping that we can get only due to RefMet in the following table.

Table 2: Final comparison of metabolite annotation and Reactome coverage after applying the full workflow.

Dataset	Number of compounds	Number of compounds with ChEBI	Number of compounds mapping to Reactome	Number of pathways	Average pathways per metabolite	Average metabolites per pathway
Covid-19 [1]	1029	685->925	114->781	478->1270	12.02->20.48	2.84->10.02
IBD [2]	473	325->454	81->413	389->892	13.59->32.58	2.83->12.46
QMDiab[3]	404	346->392	84->336	412->1161	12.02->26.48	2.44->5.44

These results highlight that pathway expansion is driven not only by an increase in mapped compounds, but also by a substantial broadening of pathway coverage per metabolite.

3. Conclusions

- The ontology-driven workflow substantially increases Reactome pathway coverage across all evaluated datasets compared to RefMet-only mapping that serves as a baseline.
- The resulting mappings enable broader and more consistent pathway-level interpretation of metabolomics datasets while maintaining chemical transparency.

Future directions:

- Systematic inspection of ontology-based generalization results can inform targeted curation guidelines by highlighting chemical classes that remain under-represented at the pathway level.
- In the evaluated datasets, lipid-related compounds constitute a substantial fraction of metabolites entering the generalization stage, indicating persistent gaps in pathway annotation for this chemical space.
- These gaps could be addressed either through focused manual curation of high-impact lipid subclasses or through the development of alternative strategies that explicitly quantify and account for lipid-driven generalization effects.
- Incorporating class-specific evaluation metrics may further improve interpretability by distinguishing genuine biological signal from annotation-driven generalization artifacts.

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